

On Q^* s - regular spaces and Q^* s - normal spaces

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Abstract

The notion of Q^* - open sets in a topological space was introduced by Murugalingam and Lalitha [7]. We introduce the notion of Q^* s - regular, Q^* s - normal, s^*Q^* - normal and obtain some characterizations Q^* s - regularity and Q^* s - normality, s^*Q^* - normal.

Keywords: Q^* s - regular; Q^* s - normal; s^*Q^* - normal; Q^* - normal.

1. Introduction :

In 1963, Levine introduced the concept of semi - open sets. Since then , a considerable number of papers discussing separation axioms, essentially by replacing open sets by semi-open sets, have appeared in the literature. For instance, Maheshwari and Prasad introduced semi- T_0 , semi- T_1 , semi- T_2 , s - normality and s - regularity as a generalization of T_0 , T_1 , T_2 , regularity and normality axioms respectively, and investigated their properties. The notion of semi-open sets was used by Maheshwari and Prasad to introduce pairwise semi- T_0 , pairwise semi- T_1 , pairwise semi- T_2 , pairwise s - regular and pairwise s -normal spaces. Moreover, s - normal (resp. semi normal) spaces were introduced and studied by Maheshwari and Prasad [6] (resp. Dorsett [3]). The concept of g - closed sets was also considered by Dunham and Levine in 1980. In 2002, Rao and Joseph introduced the concept of s^*g - closed sets. The notion of Q^* - open sets in a topological space was introduced by Murugalingam and Lalitha [7]. We introduce the notion of Q^* s - regular, Q^* s - normal and obtain some characterizations Q^* s - regularity and Q^* s - normality.

2. Preliminaries :

Definition 2.1 [13]: A space X is said to be **gs - regular** if for every g - closed set F and a point $x \notin F$, there exist disjoint semi-open sets U and V such that $x \in U$ and $F \subseteq V$.

Definition 2.2: A space X is said to be **s - normal [6] (resp. semi normal [3])** if for any two disjoint closed sets A and B , there exist disjoint semi open sets U and V such that $A \subseteq U$ and $B \subseteq V$.

Definition 2.3 [5]: A space X is said to be **s^* - normal** if for any two disjoint semi - closed sets A and B , there exist disjoint semi open sets U and V such that $A \subseteq U$ and $B \subseteq V$.

Definition 2.4 [12]: A space X is said to be **gs - normal** if for any two disjoint g - closed sets A and B , there exist disjoint semi open sets U and V such that $A \subseteq U$ and $B \subseteq V$.

Definition 2.5 [7] - Let (X , τ) be a topological space . The set of all Q^* - closed sets with X is a topology. It is denoted by $\tau_{Q^*} = \sigma^*$.

3. Q^* s - regular spaces

Definition 3.1 : A space X is said to **Q^* s - regular** if for every Q^* - closed set F and a point $x \notin F$, there exist disjoint semi-open sets U and V such that $x \in U$ and $F \subseteq V$.

Clearly, every Q^* s - regular space is gs - regular but converse is not true.

Example 3.1 : Let $X = \{ a, b, c \}$, $\tau = \{ \phi, X, \{ a \}, \{ b \}, \{ a, b \} \}$

$SO(X, \tau) = \{ \phi, X, \{ a \}, \{ b \}, \{ b, c \}, \{ a, c \}, \{ a, b \} \}$ and $\sigma^* = \{ \phi, X, \{ a, b \} \}$. Then the space X is Q^* s - regular .

Example 3.2 : Let $X = \{ a, b, c \}$, $\tau = \{ \phi, X, \{ c \}, \{ a, c \} \}$. $SO(X, \tau) = \{ \phi, X, \{ b, c \}, \{ a, c \}, \{ c \} \}$. $GC(X, \tau) = \{ \phi, X, \{ b \}, \{ a, b \}, \{ b, c \} \}$. Hence the space is gs - regular but not Q^* s - regular. Here $\{ b, c \}$ is not Q^* closed.

Theorem 3.1 : For a space X , the following are equivalent:

- X is Q^* s - regular.
- For each $x \in X$ and every Q^* - open set U containing x , there exists a semi - open set G such that $x \in G \subseteq \text{scl } G \subseteq U$.
- For every Q^* - closed set F , the intersection of all semi - closed semi neighborhoods of F is exactly F .
- For every set A and a Q^* - open set B such that $A \cap B \neq \phi$, there exists a semi open set G such that $A \cap G \neq \phi$ and $\text{scl } G \subseteq B$.
- For every non empty set A and any Q^* - closed set B satisfying $A \cap B = \phi$, there exist disjoint semi - open sets G and M such that $A \cap G \neq \phi$, and $B \subseteq M$.

Proof :

(a) \rightarrow (b) : Let $x \in U$ and U is Q^* - open in X . Therefore, $x \notin X - U$ and $X - U$ is Q^* - closed in X . Since X is Q^* s - regular, there exist disjoint semi - open sets G and H such that $x \in G$ and $X - U \subseteq H$. Now $G \subseteq X - H \subseteq U$. Since H is semi - open, therefore $\text{scl}(X - H) = X - H$. Hence $x \in G \subseteq \text{scl } G \subseteq U$.

(b) \rightarrow (c) : Let F be a Q^* - closed subset of X and $x \notin F$. Then $X - F$ is a Q^* - open set containing x . Therefore, by (b) there exists a semi - open set G such that $x \in G \subseteq \text{scl } G \subseteq X - F$. Hence, $F \subseteq X - \text{scl } G \subseteq X - G$ and $x \notin X - G$. Thus $X - G$ is a semi - closed semi - neighborhood of F which does not contain x . Hence, the intersection of all semi - closed semi - neighborhoods of F is exactly F .

(c) \rightarrow (d) : Let A be a non empty subset of X and B be a Q^* - open set such that $A \cap B \neq \phi$. Let $x \in A \cap B$. Then $X - B$ is a Q^* - closed such that $x \notin X - B$. Therefore, by (c), there exists a semi - closed semi - neighborhood of $X - B$, say V , such that $x \notin V$. Thus for the semi - closed set V , there exists a semi - open set U such that $X - B \subseteq U \subseteq V$. Take $G = X - V$. Then G is a semi - open set containing x . Also $A \cap G \neq \phi$. Now, $\text{scl } G = \text{scl}(X - V) \subseteq X - U \subseteq B$. Hence $\text{scl } G \subseteq B$.

(d) \rightarrow (e) : Let $A \cap B = \phi$, where A is non empty and B is a Q^* - closed, then $A \cap X - B \neq \phi$, where $X - B$ is a Q^* - open set. Therefore by (d), there exists a semi open set G such that $A \cap G \neq \phi$, and $G \subseteq \text{scl } G \subseteq X - B$. Now, put $M = X - \text{scl } G$. Then $B \subseteq M$ and G and M are semi - open sets such that $G \cap M = \phi$.

(e) \rightarrow (a) : Let F be a Q^* - closed subset of X and $x \notin F$. Then $\{ x \}$ and F are disjoint.

Therefore by (e), there exist disjoint semi - open sets G and M such that $\{ x \} \cap G \neq \phi$, and $F \subseteq M$. Thus $x \in G$ and $F \subseteq M$. Hence X is Q^* s - regular.

Definition 3.2 : A space X is said to **Q^* - symmetric** if $\{ x \}$ is Q^* - closed for each $x \in X$.

Theorem 3.2 : Every Q^* s - regular Q^* - symmetric space is semi - T_2 .

Proof : Let x, y be any two distinct points of X . Since X is Q^* - symmetric implies $\{ x \}$ is Q^* - closed. Also $y \notin \{ x \}$. Since X is Q^* s - regular, there exist semi - open sets U and V such that $x \in V, y \in U$ and $U \cap V = \phi$. Hence X is semi - T_2 .

Theorem 3.3 : Let $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is a homeomorphism. Then X is Q^* s - regular if and only if Y is Q^* s - regular.

Proof : Let Y be Q^* s - regular and let G be any Q^* - closed set in X such that $x \notin G$. Then $y \notin f(G)$, where $f(G)$ is a Q^* - closed set in Y . By Q^* s - regularity, there exist disjoint semi-open sets U and V in Y such that $y \in U$ and $f(G) \subseteq V$, which implies that $x \in f^{-1}(U)$ and $G \subseteq f^{-1}(V)$. In addition, $f^{-1}(U)$ and $f^{-1}(V)$ are

semi - open sets , since f is homeomorphism implies f is semi - homeomorphism implies f is irresolute. Hence X is Q^*s - regular. Also $f^{-1}(U) \cap f^{-1}(V) = \phi$. Hence, X is Q^*s - regular.

Conversely, Let X be Q^*s - regular. Let F be any Q^* - closed subset in Y such that $y \notin F$. Then $x \notin f^{-1}(F)$, where $y = f(x)$ and $f^{-1}(F)$ is Q^* - closed , since f is homeomorphism. By Q^*s -regularity, there exist disjoint semi - open sets U and V such that $x \in U, f^{-1}(F) \subseteq V$. Hence, $y \in f(U)$ and $F \subseteq f(V)$. However, $f(U)$ and $f(V)$ are semi - open sets; since f is homeomorphism implies f is semi homeomorphism, implies f is pre-semi open. Also $f(U) \cap f(V) = \phi$. Hence, Y is Q^*s - regular.

4. Q^*S - normal spaces

By replacing g closed sets by Q^* - closed sets in gs - normality due to sharma [shar], we introduce a new concept of Q^*s - normality.

Definition 4.1: A space X is said to **Q^* - normal** if for any two disjoint Q^* - closed sets A and B , there exist disjoint Q^* - open sets U and V such that $A \subseteq U$ and $B \subseteq V$.

Definition 4.2 : A space X is said to **Q^*S - normal** if for any two disjoint Q^* - closed sets A and B , there exist disjoint semi - open sets U and V such that $A \subseteq U$ and $B \subseteq V$.

Example 4.1: Let $X = \{ a, b, c \}, \tau = \{ \phi, X, \{ a \}, \{ a, c \}, \{ a, b \} \}$

$SO(X, \tau) = \sigma^* = \{ \phi, X, \{ a \}, \{ a, c \}, \{ a, b \} \}$. Then the space X is Q^*s - normal.

Example 4.2: Let $X = \{ a, b, c \}, \tau = \{ \phi, X, \{ a, c \}, \{ b, c \} \}$. $SO(X, \tau) = \{ \phi, X, \{ a, c \}, \{ b, c \} \}$. Hence the space X is Q^*S - normal .

Definition 4.3: A space X is said to be **S^*Q^* - normal** if for every pair of disjoint semi closed sets A & B in X , there exists disjoint Q^* open sets U & V such that $A \subseteq U$ and $B \subseteq V$.

Definition 4.4 : (i) A space (X, τ) is called *weakly Q^* - normal* if disjoint Q^* - closed sets can be separated by disjoint closed sets.

(ii) A function $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is said to be *always Q^* - closed* if the image of each Q^* - closed set in (X, τ) is Q^* - closed in (Y, σ) .

Example 4.3: In example 3.2 , X is S^*Q^* - normal .

Theorem 4.1: For a space X the following are equivalent:

- X is Q^*S - normal.
- For each Q^* closed set F and a Q^* - open set K containing F , there exists a semi open set U such that $F \subseteq U \subseteq scl U \subseteq K$.
- For every Q^* closed set A and a Q^* closed set B disjoint from A , there exists a semi - open set U containing A such that $scl U \cap B = \phi$.

Proof :

a) \rightarrow b) : Let X be Q^*s - normal and let K be a Q^* - open set containing a Q^* - closed set F . Then F and $X - K$ are disjoint Q^* - closed sets. So by (a), there exists a semi-open set U and a semi-open set V such that $F \subseteq U, X - K \subseteq V$ and $U \cap V = \phi$. Thus $U \subseteq X - V$, which implies that $scl U \subseteq X - V$. Hence, $F \subseteq U \subseteq scl U \subseteq K$.

b) \rightarrow c) : Let A and B are Q^* - closed subsets of X such that $A \cap B = \phi$, which implies $A \subseteq X - B$, a Q^* - open set. So by (b), there exists a semi-open set U such that $A \subseteq U \subseteq scl U \subseteq X - B$. Hence, $scl U \cap B = \phi$.

c) \rightarrow a) : Let A and B be disjoint Q^* - closed sets. Then, by (c), there is a semi - open set U such that $A \subseteq U$ and $scl U \cap B = \phi$. Now $scl U$ is semi-closed. Hence, $B \subseteq X - scl U$, let $V = X - scl U$. Then V is a semi-open set such that $B \subseteq V$ and $U \cap V = \phi$. Hence, X is Q^*s - normal.

Theorem 4.2 : For a space X the following are equivalent:

- X is S^*Q^* - normal.
- For each semi - closed set F and a semi - open set K containing F , there exists a Q^* - open set U such that $F \subseteq U \subseteq \sigma^* - cl(U) \subseteq K$.

- c) For every semi - closed set A and a semi closed set B disjoint from A, there exists a Q^* - open set U containing A such that $\sigma^* - cl (U) \cap B = \phi$.

Proof :

a) \rightarrow b) : Let X be S^*Q^* - normal and let K be a semi - open set containing a semi - closed set F. Then F and $X - K$ are disjoint semi - closed sets. So by (a), there exists a Q^* - open set U and a Q^* - open set V such that $F \subseteq U$, $X - K \subseteq V$ and $U \cap V = \phi$. Thus $U \subseteq X - V$, which implies that $\sigma^* - cl (U) \subseteq X - V$. Hence, $F \subseteq U \subseteq \sigma^* - cl (U) \subseteq K$.

b) \rightarrow c) : Let A and B are semi - closed subsets of X such that $A \cap B = \phi$, which implies $A \subseteq X - B$, a semi - open set. So by (b), there exists a Q^* - open set U such that $A \subseteq U \subseteq \sigma^* - cl (U) \subseteq X - B$. Hence, $\sigma^* - cl (U) \cap B = \phi$.

c) \rightarrow a) : Let A and B be disjoint semi - closed sets . Then , by c) , there is a Q^* - open set U such that $A \subseteq U$ and $\sigma^* - cl (U) \cap B = \phi$. Now $\sigma^* - cl (U)$ is Q^* - closed. Hence, $B \subseteq X - \sigma^* - cl (U)$, let $V = X - \sigma^* - cl (U)$. Then V is a Q^* - open set such that $B \subseteq V$ and $U \cap V = \phi$. Hence, X is S^*Q^* - normal.

Theorem 4.3 : Every Q^* s - normal Q^* - symmetric space X is Q^* s - regular.

Proof: Let F be a Q^* - closed subset of X with $x \in F$. Since X is Q^* - symmetric so $\{ x \}$ is Q^* - closed. So $\{ x \}$ and F are disjoint Q^* - closed sets in X. Since X is Q^* S - normal , there exist disjoint semi - open sets U and V such that $\{ x \} \subseteq U$, $F \subseteq V$. Hence X is Q^* S - regular.

Theorem 4.4 : Every Q^* - normal Q^* - symmetric space X is Q^* - regular.

Proof: Let F be a Q^* - closed subset of X with $x \in F$. Since X is Q^* - symmetric so $\{ x \}$ is Q^* - closed. So $\{ x \}$ and F are disjoint Q^* - closed sets in X. Since X is Q^* - normal , there exist disjoint Q^* - open sets U and V such that $\{ x \} \subseteq U$, $F \subseteq V$. Hence X is Q^* - regular.

Theorem 4.3 : Let $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is a homeomorphism. Then X is Q^* S - normal if and only if Y is Q^* S - normal.

Proof : Let Y be Q^* s - normal. Let A and B be two disjoint Q^* - closed sets in X. Then $f (A)$ and $f (B)$ are Q^* - closed sets in Y. Since Y is Q^* s - normal , there exist disjoint semi - open sets U and V in Y such that $f (A) \subseteq U$, $f (B) \subseteq V$. Hence, $A \subseteq f^{-1} (U)$, $B \subseteq f^{-1} (V)$, and $f^{-1} (U) \cap f^{-1} (V) = \phi$ as $U \cap V = \phi$. Moreover, $f^{-1} (U)$ and $f^{-1} (V)$ are semi - open sets; since f is homeomorphism implies f is semi homeomorphism implies f is an irresolute map. Hence X is Q^* s - normal.

Conversely, Let X is Q^* s - normal . Let A and B be two disjoint Q^* - closed sets in Y. Then $f^{-1} (A)$ and $f^{-1} (B)$ are Q^* - closed sets in X . Since X is Q^* s - normal , there exist disjoint semi-open sets U and V in X such that $f^{-1} (A) \subseteq U$, $f^{-1} (B) \subseteq V$. Hence $A \subseteq f (U)$, $B \subseteq f (V)$, and $f (U) \cap f (V) = \phi$ as $U \cap V = \phi$. However , $f (U)$ and $f (V)$ are semi - open sets ; since f is homeomorphism implies f is semi-homeomorphism implies f is pre - semi open. Hence, Y is Q^* s -normal.

5. Comparison

Remark 5.1 : We summarize the relationship between various special types of normal spaces in the following diagram . None of the implications is reversible.

Theorem 5.1 : Every Q^*S - normal space is S - normal.

Proof : Let X be a Q^*s - normal space . To show that X is S - normal . Let A and B be two disjoint Q^* closed sets. Since X is Q^*s - normal, there exists disjoint semi - open sets U and V such that $A \subseteq U$ and $B \subseteq V$. Since every Q^* closed set is closed we have A and B are closed sets. Hence X is s - normal.

Remark 5.2 : Converse of the above theorem need not be true in general.

Example 5.2 : Let $X = \{ a, b, c \}$, $\tau = \{ \phi, X, \{ a \}, \{ b \}, \{ a, b \} \}$.

$SO(X, \tau) = \{ \phi, X, \{ a \}, \{ b \}, \{ a, c \}, \{ a, b \}, \{ b, c \} \}$. Here $\{ b, c \}$ is closed but not Q^* - closed . Hence the space X is S - normal but not Q^*S - normal.

Theorem 5.2 : Every S^*Q^* - normal space is Semi - normal.

Proof : Let X be a S^*Q^* - normal space . To show that X is S - normal . Let A and B be two disjoint semi - closed sets . Since X is S^*Q^* - normal, there exists disjoint Q^* - open sets U and V such that $A \subseteq U$ and $B \subseteq V$. Since every Q^* - open set is semi - open, there exists disjoint semi - open sets U and V such that $A \subseteq U$ and $B \subseteq V$. Hence X is semi - normal.

Remark 5.3 : But the converse of the above theorem need not be true in general.

Example 5.3 : In example 5.2 , $\{ b \}$ is semi open but not Q^* - open . Hence the space X is semi normal but not Q^*s normal.

Theorem 5.3 : Every Q^* - normal space is Q^*s - normal.

Proof : Let X be a Q^* - normal space . To show that X is Q^*s - normal . Let A and B be two disjoint Q^* - closed sets . Since X is pairwise Q^* - normal , there exists disjoint Q^* - open sets U and V such that $A \subseteq U$ and $B \subseteq V$. Since every Q^* - open set is semi - open , there exists disjoint semi - open sets U and V such that $A \subseteq U$ and $B \subseteq V$. Hence X is Q^*s - normal .

Remark 5.4 : But the converse of the above theorem need not be true in general.

Theorem 5.4 : Every Q^*s - normal space is gs - normal.

Proof : Let X be a Q^*s - normal space . To show that X is gs - normal . Let A and B be two disjoint Q^* closed sets . Since X is Q^*s - normal , there exists disjoint semi - open sets U and V such that $A \subseteq U$ and $B \subseteq V$. Since every Q^* closed set is g - closed we have A and B are g - closed sets . Hence X is gs - normal.

Remark 5.5 : Converse of the above theorem need not be true in general.

Example 5.4 : In example 3.2 , $\{ b, c \}$ is g closed but not Q^* closed . Hence the space X is gs normal but not Q^*s normal.

Conclusion :

The notion of Q^*s - regular , Q^*s - normal , s^*Q^* - normal in topological space has been generalized and obtain some characterizations Q^*s - regularity and Q^*s - normality , s^*Q^* - normal . These notions can be applied for investigating many other properties.

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